

TECHNOLOGICAL FEATURES OF THE SULFATION PROCESS OF ALKYLBENZOLS WITH SULFATE ANHYDRIDE

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Abstract. During the research, sulfonation process forms sulfons. Their content in sulfonic acid is very little dependent on the technological regime parameters and constitutes about 1% of the total mass, but at a CO₃/AB molar ratio greater than 1.08, their formation rate increases sharply.

Keywords: sulfonation process, sulfons, hydrocarbons, alkylbenzenes, side chain, electrophilic substitution mechanism

The production of sulfonic acids, which are currently used in various fields of science, in the processes of sulfonation of hydrocarbons is discussed in various sources. [1] The research results examine methods for sulfonating toluene and ethylbenzene with sulfuric anhydride, sulfuric acid, and sulfuric anhydride in the presence of methanesulfonic acid. [2] describe methods for sulfonating olefins, including using photocatalysts, as well as methods for obtaining sulfonic acids, which are essential amino acids, using a stable SO₃·DMF complex as a sulfonating agent. [3] The works present the results of studies on the processes of sulfonation of alcohols, amines, and phenols with sulfonyl chloride to obtain sulfo compounds used in pharmacology. [4] The literature is devoted to the optimization of the sulfonation process of alkylbenzenes with a side chain length of C₉-C₁₃ carbon atoms (molecular mass 230-245 g/mol), including using mathematical methods

Organic raw materials - alkylbenzenes with the formula R-C₆H₅, where R is the radical of the n-paraffin molecule with a carbon atom number from 10 to 13, react with sulfur anhydride in the reactor, resulting in the formation of sulfonic acid according to the following reaction:

In addition to the above, side reactions can also occur, in which other types of sulfonic acids, such as sulfonic anhydride or PSA, are formed.

Additionally, sulfonation process produces sulfons. Their quantity in sulfuric acid depends very little on the parameters of the technological regime and is about 1% of the total mass, however, their formation rate increases sharply when the molar ratio of SO₃/AB exceeds 1.08. Sulfones have the following structural formula:

When forming sulfonic acid, the indicated compounds, except for sulfons, decompose or react directly with the AB residue or, upon mixing, are hydrolyzed with water according to the following reactions:

High concentrations of SO_3 and high molar ratios of $SO_3:AB$ also lead to the dealkylation of alkylbenzene with the formation of unsaturated hydrocarbons (olefins), which polymerize to form resinous compounds, thereby deteriorating the color of sulfonic acid.

Regarding the mechanism of sulfonation reactions, there are currently several hypotheses:

1. Electrophilic substitution mechanism. This assumption is based on the fact that at the first stage of the aromatic compound sulfonation mechanism, intermediate p- and s-complexes are formed due to the electrophilic attack of the carbon atom by the sulfuric anhydride molecule.

This reaction proceeds very quickly and is a first-order reaction, the rate of which depends on the diffusion factors, as well as the intensity of mixing and the removal of the released heat.

2. Another assumption is that the sulfonation reaction of aromatic compounds begins with the interaction of a mixture of sulfur trioxide and alkylbenzenes, leading to the formation of intermediate compounds ABSA and PSA.

The mechanism of the primary reaction of a mixture of linear alkylbenzenes with SO_3 is presented below.

Further, the alkylbenzene mixture reacts with PSC to form two moles of ABSA. In this case, one mole-equivalent is considered as a product of the first stage, and the second as a contribution to increasing conversion.

In this basic reaction, pyrosulfonic acid acts as a sulfonating agent.

The intermediate product - sulfonic acid anhydride and PSA - are then reacted with a mixture of alkylbenzenes or water to obtain the target product - sulfonic acid.

The technological scheme of the plant for sulfonation of alkylbenzenes with sulfur anhydride is presented in Figure 1. ABSA production is carried out on two parallel technological lines, each of which consists of three main technological units.

In the gas mixture preparation section, liquid sulfur is burned in a furnace with excess dried air, resulting in sulfur dioxide (SO_2). Further, SO_2 is converted into SO_3 in a special apparatus - a converter, in the flow of dried air above the catalyst layer (V_2O_5). Dried air participates in the process, as humid air forms sulfuric acid with SO_3 , which leads to the breakdown of the technology and increases equipment corrosion.

The sulfonation unit is designed to obtain alkylbenzenesulfonic acids - ABSK by the interaction of a gas-air mixture of SO_3 and alkylbenzenes in the reactor in film mode. The resulting alkylbenzenesulfonic acids, after stabilization and hydrolysis, are transported to the raw material department.

Raw materials (alkylbenzenes) are fed into buffer tanks at a constant level. The temperature of alkylbenzenes is maintained constant.

To remove a constant level of alkylbenzenes from the tank, they are pumped into cartridge filters, where the pressure before and after the filters is measured, and a temperature sensor is installed on the line. Alkylbenzenes enter the upper part of the 120-tube multi-tube film reactor through distribution devices, the design of which ensures the uniform distribution of alkylbenzenes through the tubes and

the optimal ratio of raw materials and sulfonate gas in each reaction tube.

Figure 1. Technological scheme of the sulfuric anhydride sulfonation plant for alkylbenzenes:

1 - air drying column; 2 - furnace, 3 - converter for converting SO_2 to SO_3 ; 4 - heat exchanger; 5 - pipette; 6 - separator; 7 - ABSA capacity; 8 - multi-tube film sulfonation reactor; 9, 18 - refrigerator; 10 - cyclone for separating gas and liquid phases; 11 - Cyclone for complete purification of waste reaction gases from ABSA droplets; 12 - reservoir for storing ABSA; 13-16 - stabilization columns; 17 - ABSA mixer

The reaction gas flow, containing 5-5.5% SO_3 by volume, is evenly distributed over the pipes from top to bottom into the reactor.

The gas mixture pressure is measured before the reactor.

Pneumatic SO_3 -air mixture absorbers are installed in the reactor and the supply pipe to the absorber, and the gas mixture is automatically pumped into the absorber.

The heat is removed due to the circulation of the coolant through the reactor jacket. Water is supplied to a heat exchanger, where it is cooled by water with a temperature of 14-18°C coming from the chiller. The temperature of the heat carrier is regulated by the reactor jacket.

The pressure in the upper and lower parts of the reactor is monitored, and the flow of alkylbenzenes into the reactor is measured and controlled.

The mixture of the sulfonation product and the outgoing gas from the reactor enters the cyclone, where the separation of the gas and liquid phases occurs. A cyclone measures and maintains a constant level. The reaction gas pressure at the cyclone outlet is measured.

To compensate for water losses, a tank with level measurement and control is provided in the cooling circuit of the reactor jacket.

To further retain the unreacted SO_3 at the cyclone outlet, a nozzle is installed on the vertical section of the pipe. In nozzles, alkylbenzenes are sprayed with compressed air. Alkylbenzenes and technical air are preheated in heat

exchangers. The pressure and flow rate of alkylbenzenes in the alkylbenzene supply line are measured and regulated, and the air pressure in the heat exchanger is maintained by a pressure regulator that directly affects the air. The air and alkylbenzenes in heat exchangers are heated by water vapor, and the pressure in the steam pipe is measured.

The purification of exhaust gases from the ABSA drip feed reaction is carried out in a cyclone. Then the exhaust gases are sent to the purification stage, to the absorption and exhaust gas processing unit.

The liquid phase (LFA), if the product quality is suitable, is pumped into the LFA storage tank. The pump line is equipped with a mass flow meter with a maximum and minimum signal, a manometer, a temperature sensor, and a density analyzer with a maximum and minimum signal.

Non-standard acid is collected in a prefabricated container. The set provides level control. The dosing pump in the static mixer mixes substandard ABSA from the collection point with incoming raw materials and returns it to the reactor.

In case of violation of the technological regime, in the event of an emergency situation (disconnection of electricity, lack of raw materials, etc.), an emergency tank is installed over the reactor, which allows washing the reactor AB and preventing the products from igniting. The following parameters are monitored in the reservoir: pressure, temperature, and there is also a level drop signal.

The device for absorption and purification of exhaust gases is designed to purify exhaust gases after the sulfonation process, as well as when starting and stopping the sulfur dioxide absorption unit before releasing exhaust gases into the atmosphere.

A mixture of air with SO₃ is supplied for absorption during the start-up or shutdown of the production line. In the absorber, a reaction occurs between SO₃ and H₂O, resulting in the formation of H₂SO₄ according to the following reaction:

The sulfuric acid concentration is maintained at 97-98% by mass by supplying demineralized water to the absorber. The reaction is exothermic, therefore heat is removed in a water cooler. The resulting sulfuric acid is discharged into the reservoir.

After sulfonation, the exhaust gases contain a small amount of sulfonic acid and unreacted SO₂ and SO₃.

Then, a wet filter is used to remove organic residues and SO₃ from exhaust gases.

Further, the gaseous SO₂ and SO₃ in the gas purifier columns are neutralized with sodium hydroxide (NaOH).

The neutralization reaction of these gases is as follows:

Sodium sulfite is an unstable compound that reacts with oxygen to form sodium sulfate:

The small amounts of sulfonic and sulfuric acids remaining in the exhaust gases react in the NaOH columns as follows:

The purified exhaust gas is discharged into the atmosphere, and the utilized alkaline solution is discharged into the "KINEF" LLC sewer well. Wastewater can be pumped into the preaerator.

Table 1 presents the main technological parameters, raw material characteristics, and design features of the reactor for the sulfonation process of alkylbenzenes with sulfur anhydride.

Table 1

Parameters of the sulfonation process of alkylbenzenes

Process Options	Meaning
Properties of raw materials	
Alkylbenzenes	
Density at 15°C, kg/m ³	858-862
Mass fraction of sulfonated substances, %, not less than	98,0
Average molecular weight, kg/kmol	238,0 - 245,0
Mass fraction of linear isomers, %:	
C ₉ -benzene, not more	1,0
C ₁₀ -benzene, not more	15,0
C ₁₀ -C ₁₁ -benzene	30,0 - 55,0
C ₁₃ -C ₁₄ -benzene, not more	30,0
C ₁₄ -benzene, not more	1,0
Mass fraction of 2-phenylalkanes, %, not more than	20,0
Mass fraction of paraffins, %, not more than	0,3
Alkylbenzenesulfonic acids (grade A)	
Mass fraction of ABSA, %, not less than	96,0
Mass fraction of sulfuric acid, %, not more than	2,0
Mass fraction of unsulfonated compounds, %, not more than	2,0
Density at 50°C, kg/m ³	1010-1050
Molecular weight, kg/kmol	318,0-326,0
Sulfonating gas	
Sulfur dioxide content, % vol., not more than	5,5
Process Options	
AB consumption at the reactor inlet, kg/h	2700-4500

Molar ratio SO ₃ :AB, not more than	1,08
Mass fraction of sulfuric acid, %, not more than	2,0
Gas mixture pressure at the reactor inlet, kPa, not more than	90
High reactor pressure, kPa, not more than	90
Lower reactor pressure, kPa, not more than	10
Reaction gas temperature at reactor inlet, °C	45-50
AB temperature at reactor inlet, °C	20-45
Reactor design	
Number of pipes, units.	120
Reactor tube diameter, m	0,025
Reactor tube length, m	6

The higher the concentration of SO₃, the higher the rate of the sulfonation reaction, the more heat is released per unit time. Therefore, the concentration of SO₃ should not exceed 5.5% by volume.

Thus, in addition to the previously described reactions in the sulfonation reactor of alkylbenzenes with sulfur anhydride, the thermodynamic parameters of the reaction for the formation of by-products, including sulfons, included in the high-viscosity component, have been calculated. It has been shown that the Gibbs energy of sulfonation reactions is $\Delta G \approx 0$ kJ/mol. These reactions are included in the hydrocarbon transformation scheme and are taken into account when constructing the mathematical model of the sulfonation reactor.

Foydalanilgan rahbariy hujjatlar ro'yxati:

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